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Comprehensive machine learning approaches for modelling the state of charge of lithium-ion batteries

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HIGHLIGHTS

- MLP, LSTM and NARX are used to model SOC in LiBs with coarse datasets.
- MLP and LSTM are more adaptable with a smaller training dataset.
- Higher correlation between SOC and EIS data is found for EIS measured at 0% SOC.
- Strengths and weaknesses of the MLP, LSTM and NARX are discussed.
- Effects of training size, hidden layers and learning rates of ANNs are discussed.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The advancement of lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) is vital for achieving net-zero emissions because it enables renewable energy integration, supports electric vehicle (EV) adoption, and promotes cost-effective and sustainable solutions. The growing demand for EVs and portable electronics has amplified the need for reliable battery management systems to ensure safety and performance. Machine learning (ML) methods for modelling the state of charge (SOC) in batteries are gaining traction owing to their adaptability to diverse datasets and lower computational demands. However, the challenge lies in selecting the most suitable ML architecture for a specific application. This study evaluates three ML approaches for SOC modelling in LIBs: multilayer perceptron (MLP), long short-term memory (LSTM), and nonlinear autoregressive with exogenous input (NARX) neural networks. The models were tested using an experimental dataset with multiple input variables, including electrochemical impedance spectroscopy data, voltage, and capacity from commercial LIB cells. The results show that MLP and LSTM perform effectively with smaller training datasets (14 samples), whereas the NARX model requires more extensive data (34 out of 67 samples) for accuracy. Additionally, the NARX model showed greater sensitivity to learning rate adjustments and hidden layer configurations, whereas MLP and LSTM maintained robust performance across varying parameters.

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1. Introduction

[1] The adoption of electric vehicles (EVs), including e-scooters, e-bikes, e-trucks, and other forms of e-mobility, has experienced rapid growth worldwide over the past decade. By 2022, the number of electric cars alone on the road exceeded 26 million, marking a 60% increase compared to 2021 and surpassing more than five times the stock recorded in 2018 ([Trends in electric light-duty vehicles -- Global EV Outlook 2023 -- Analysis - IEA](#)). This growth is in line with the targets outlined in the Paris Action Agenda on Electro-Mobility and Climate Change ([The Paris Agreement | UNFCCC](#)). Upon comparing the technological readiness of batteries available in the market, it is evident that LIBs continue to dominate [2,3]. Comparative analysis of diverse battery chemistries is rooted in critical factors, including energy density, power density, cycle life, calendar life, and cost per kWh. An assessment based on these parameters underscores the preeminence of LIBs as a leading technology in the foreseeable future, boasting superior energy density, efficiency, and an extended lifespan. In addition, LIBs display the potential for noteworthy short-term enhancement [2,4,5]. Nevertheless, the effective performance of the battery can be significantly compromised by sudden temperature changes, and incidents such as fire and battery destruction are common consequences of overcharging [1,2,4,6]. These aspects raise serious safety concerns, particularly when considering the use of LIBs in EVs. Moreover, meeting the increased demand for LIBs and the enlarged complexity of the LIBs architecture requires the development of highly accurate estimation of and reliable battery management systems (BMSs). The BMS plays a vital role in estimating the state of charge (SOC) and state of health (SOH) of the battery, respectively; the ability of the battery to deliver its specific output, and the remaining useful life [2]. Moreover, it can accurately assess battery ageing and degradation [7]. The SOC for a battery in use is estimated using highly correlated external variables, such as voltage, current, charge, and impedance [7,8]. Advanced mathematical models can estimate the battery SOC based on the aforementioned externally measured variables. The benefit of taking external measurements is that the battery performance is not affected by the measurements, and variables can be observed without disabling the battery [9].

Recent applications of LIBs present new circumstances that may require unique or revised models. Therefore, a plethora of SOC models are now available to the public and industry. Most types of modelling techniques fall under the following umbrella terms: direct methods, adaptive methods, bookkeeping methods, and hybrid methods. Existing SOC estimation techniques, such as Coulomb counting, open-circuit voltage, and Kalman filter methods, present significant drawbacks in real-life applications. The limitations of these example methods include the following: Coulomb counting is susceptible to cumulative errors due to inaccuracies in current measurement and initial SOC estimation; open-circuit voltage requires the battery to be at rest for accurate measurement, which is impractical for in-use BMS applications; and Kalman filter methods, while accurate, are computationally intensive and heavily reliant on precise battery models, making them sensitive to parameter variations and uncertainties [10]. Advancements continue to be made in Kalman filter models [11] to reduce computational cost and noise reduction to improve modelling capabilities. The methods used in research on existing techniques can also be applied to improve ML approaches [12,13]. Artificial neural networks (ANN) and ML approaches effectively address these challenges by modelling nonlinear battery behaviour, reducing susceptibility to noise, and adapting to diverse operating conditions. In addition, ANNs facilitate real-time SOC estimation without requiring battery rest. Several advanced ANN models developed in [12–14] address the challenges of real-life applications, such as noise reduction, improved feature extraction, and reduced computational cost. While ANNs often exhibit limitations in

modelling with coarse datasets, this paper presents improvements on ANN applications to coarse data for SOC prediction using the most basic ANNs to highlight the impact of their unique architectural differences. ANN and ML methods appeal to the scientific community because of their ability to adapt and detect underlying patterns using simple computations. ML models require no physical understanding of the system and work effectively with a much lower computational cost than alternative models such as the Kalman filter method. These two factors have attracted the attention of many scientific researchers [15,16]. In recent studies [17–19], it has been demonstrated that there is potential to implement physics-informed ANNs for modelling various internal components of the battery, such as long-term changes [17,18] or SOC, as in [19]. For accurate predictions, the latter used a large dataset, as opposed to the coarse dataset used in this study. Further uses for machine learning in the field of batteries and greener energy include the development and improvement of energy storage materials via ML methods [20,21]. The ML methods discussed in this study use an ANN approach within the ML family.

The aim of an ANN model is to mimic the natural structure and process, that is, the processing of information by the brain's network of neural pathways and synapses. ANNs are designed to train themselves by implementing a learning algorithm that essentially uses the error between the predicted output (initially the result of random neuron activation) and the true output of a training dataset [22]. This validation between the predicted and true values guides the hidden layer to form a bias, or weight, on each synapse that reduces the output error. If the structure and initial conditions of the ANN are relatively appropriate, extensive repetition will cause the ANN output to converge to a minimum error, thereby providing an accurate model for the desired output. This is tested against the reserved test data to judge the model's predictive ability fairly. ANNs face limitations such as being trapped in local minima that are far from the global minimum, overfitting the model to the training data, and thus failing to make predictions with new data [23].

A plethora of available neural network (NN) architectures can render the selection of an appropriate design challenging. It is also common to struggle to fix the correct layer sizes and learning algorithms [16]. This is true for individuals that are educated in the field, let alone individuals who are not familiar with the needs and functions of NN modelling [24]. While initial judgement can narrow down the selection of NN architectures, the validation of the remaining selection and choice is often accomplished by trial and error [24]. The aim of this study was to investigate three different neural networks: multilayer perceptron (MLP), long short-term memory (LSTM), and nonlinear auto-regressive with exogenous input (NARX). These three models were selected for investigation based on their key differences: The MLP was chosen as an indicator for the existing modified MLP designs and serves as a stepping stone for the investigation of more advanced MLP based ANN models. LSTM possesses the ability to detect both long- and short-term trends; this characteristic is used to provide a basis for informing the reader of the potential for further investigation of subtle patterns between the input parameters and SOC. NARX was selected to investigate the temporal dependency of the dataset used in the ANN for SOC prediction. The NARX feedback loop, as discussed later, uniquely preserves the temporal relationship between the input and output values for making the next prediction. While numerous alternative ANN models exist in the literature, the authors determined the basic MLP, NARX, and LSTM models to be a suitable indication and stepping stone for future research into more advanced techniques, specifically for applications with coarse datasets. The adaptability and flexibility of the models were assessed, and the performances when predicting the SOC were analysed and compared. Similar to a previous study [25], the flexibility of different ML methods is expanded by addressing different aspects. The sensitivity and flexibility of the learning rate, layer sizes,

training percentages, and overall performance were compared for each NN design. The EIS and voltage measurements of a Samsung INR18650-35E LIB were used for training and validating the models. The outcomes of this paper will inform the reader of the behaviour of these three NN architectures and will guide towards an enlightened decision about which model to use when fitting the data. Furthermore, this paper attempts to outline the possibility of reducing experimental labour, materials, expenses, and waste.

2. Machine learning (ML)

This section provides a brief overview of ML concepts to prepare the reader for elaborations and justifications made in the **Results and Discussions** section. The section introduces basic concepts using an example of a feedforward NN, including the activation function, optimisation algorithms, and weights. We then introduce the three ML approaches applied in this study, that is, MLP, LSTM, and NARX NNs, and the details of each network-specific layer process.

ML approaches use mathematical algorithms to train a particular model such that it can predict the output of a certain process given specified input variables [15,22,26–29]. The NN field of ML is inspired by the natural processes of organic brains [22]. That is, an NN comprises several layers that contain a collection of synapses or nodes linked together via neural paths or connections. Hence, NNs in ML are often called ANNs to distinguish them from biological ones. External information is processed as it flows from the initial *input* layer → *hidden* layers → *output* or *decision* layer. An ANN uses technology to construct an information processing system that mimics this structure and uses mathematical functions to interpret and assign data throughout the evolving ANN. An ANN can be structured with various architectures and functions that uniquely process the input data to provide an output. Their differences in design are useful for the specific characteristic behaviours of the dataset. Selecting the appropriate architecture will help the model perform within reasonable error bounds. However, similar to the human brain, any ANN requires training to function appropriately. Training an ANN involves reducing or increasing the weight or bias of each synapse within the network such that the output approaches a minimum error. The weight represents the importance or correlation strength between the node and output, and it is adjusted after every iteration. Unlike the weights, the bias is more rigid and portrays a firmly implemented relation between nodes and outputs; it is not adjusted as freely as the weights. Not all NNs include bias. For most NNs, the initial distribution of node weights within the hidden layer is random, and they are adjusted when the error is propagated back through the network. The output accuracy is a matter of assigning the correct weights to each individual synapse, thus identifying the true underlying patterns in the dataset. Many mathematical algorithms have been developed to determine the optimal weight distribution; these are called *training algorithms* [30,31]. The most suitable training algorithm depends on the behaviour of the dataset and the NN architecture and is often determined after exploring many possibilities [30].

2.1. Basic architecture: Feedforward neural network (FNN)

The FNN is the most basic NN structure, as shown in Fig. 1(a). It consists of an input layer, a hidden layer, and an output layer. The hidden layer does not need to be “fully connected” to be classified as an FNN; a fully connected layer will have all synapses connected to every synapse of the subsequent layer. Any NN input layer must connect to the hidden layer via activation functions and assign weights to each node. The final hidden layer of any NN must be fully connected to the output layer, in this case a single node that presents the predicted SOC. Furthermore, the hidden layer can consist of any number of nodes; however, fewer nodes will desirably reduce the number of computations. An error term is found by comparing the predicted and experimental outputs, and then the error is fed through the network to adjust the weights using the training algorithm.

2.2. Pattern recognition and data extraction

ANNs are famous for their ability to process data and evolve into models that can accurately predict an outcome beyond the comprehension of alternative physics-informed models. The hidden layer of an ANN is labelled as such for its unobservable nature. The specific patterns, trends, and relationships that the ANN detects during the training process are hidden within the hidden layers of the ANN and cannot be extracted. Much research is underway to uncover knowledge in ANNs [32–34]. The recognition of new patterns by an ANN is most obvious during the fine-tuning of the ANN parameters. As one begins to optimise the model, the error curve (difference between the predicted and known data points) will smooth. The smoothing of the error curve is indicative of an ANN learning new and subtle trends within a dataset. A key parameter affecting the detection of subtle patterns is the learning rate. As the learning rate decreases, an ANN is able to navigate into small local error minima, whereas a larger learning rate would cause the ANN to oscillate around the minimum or skip over it entirely. Despite difficulties in extracting the inner workings of ANNs, the ability to form these subtle patterns that exceed the comprehension of physical and mathematical theories is extremely valuable and marks a cornerstone to the success of ANN modelling performances.

2.3. Activation functions

An activation function maps the values from the respective nodes to a specific domain. Its purpose is to manipulate the data such that it fits a desired distribution to improve the functionality of the model-training algorithm. Popular activation functions applied in NNs include the sigmoid (σ), tan-sigmoid (tansig), rectified linear (ReLU), and hyperbolic tan (tanh) functions [35,36]. The sigmoid function converts the input data to $x \in [0, 1]$ along the sigmoid curve given by

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}.$$

Alternatively, the tansig function maps $x \in [-1, 1]$ using a combination of the tan and sigmoid functions:

$$\text{tansig}(x) = \frac{2}{1 + e^{-2x}} - 1.$$

Both are good for taking any input value. However, the ReLU function is stricter because it maps all negative input values to 0 and all other values remain the same.

Finally, the tanh function is the familiar function

$$\tanh(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}},$$

which also maps any input $x \in [-1, 1]$ along the alternative tanh(x) curve.

During this study, the tansig activation function was identified as the common function with a high accuracy output between all models. Using consistent activation functions where possible helped streamline the comparison of architectural impacts between the models.

2.4. Adam optimiser

Learning algorithms in NNs are an essential component of ML. The purpose of the learning algorithm is to guide the network towards minimal error by comparing the network output and the true output and using statistical error measurements to adjust the network accordingly [37]. The common stochastic gradient descent (SGD) is the basis from which the Adam algorithm was constructed [38]. It is a gradient-based optimisation method with simple computations that can be labelled as an adaptive moment estimation algorithm – “Adam” [38]. The Adam optimiser updates the weights of the NN with Eq. (1) [39]:

$$w_t = w_{t-1} - \alpha \frac{\hat{m}_t}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_t + \epsilon}}, \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of (a), the basic feedforward NN architecture showing the nodes and weights of each layer connected by straight line neural paths; and (b), the architecture of a general multilayer perceptron NN.

where w is the weight vector of the hidden layer and α is the initial learning rate, which is constant in this application. m and v are moving averages and ϵ is a small positive constant, typically 10^{-8} , to avoid any division by zero (exploding gradient). The moving averages m_t and v_t are the exponential averages of the gradient along w_t and the exponential averages of the squares of gradients along w_t (otherwise known as *aggregate* - the exponential average of the previous gradient g_{t-1} and present gradient g_t). \hat{m}_t and \hat{v}_t are then given as

$$m_t = \alpha m_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha)g_t,$$

$$\hat{m}_t = \frac{m_t}{(1 - \alpha^t)}, \quad (2)$$

$$v_t = \mu v_{t-1} + (1 - \mu)g_t^2,$$

$$\hat{v}_t = \frac{v_t}{(1 - \mu^t)}. \quad (3)$$

where α and μ are the *hyperparameters* of the Adam optimiser. The learning rate α and gradient decay rate μ for the selected NNs in this study are displayed in Table 1.

The training of the models in this study used the Adam optimiser and the remaining training parameters were identified through trial and error as described in Section 2.6.

2.5. Approach 1: Long short term memory (LSTM)

A long short-term memory (LSTM) NN follows the simple recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture with an additional memory component. That is, the LSTM NN includes the input, LSTM, hidden, and output layers. The purpose of the LSTM layer is to hold data in storage for thousands of time steps to allow long-term trends to be acknowledged. This helps the model avoid vanishing and exploding gradients and considers the sources of long-term trends.

2.5.1. LSTM layer process

The LSTM process is essentially a feedback loop with a few additional components that enable long-term memory storage. Each iteration creates a “cell state” which is used to inform the LSTM layer in the following iteration. The cell state is a function of four gates that interact with the input data: forget gate (f), retain gate (i), cell

candidate gate (g), and output gate (o). Fig. 2 presents the flow of information through the LSTM layer. The input is copied four times and plugged into each gate, where it is combined with the previous hidden state. Using x_t as the current input vector, W and R as the input and recurrent weight vectors, respectively, and the bias b of each node, the following symbolic expressions describe the data processing through the LSTM layer:

$$\text{i gate} \rightarrow i_t = \sigma(W_i x_t + R_i h_{t-1} + b_i), \quad (4)$$

$$\text{f gate} \rightarrow f_t = \sigma(W_f x_t + R_f h_{t-1} + b_f), \quad (5)$$

$$\text{g gate} \rightarrow g_t = \tanh(W_g x_t + R_g h_{t-1} + b_g), \quad (6)$$

$$\text{o gate} \rightarrow o_t = \sigma(W_o x_t + R_o h_{t-1} + b_o). \quad (7)$$

Feeding the previous hidden state h_{t-1} and current inputs x_t through these gates as in Fig. 2, the current hidden state h_t is calculated by element-wise multiplication and matrix addition:

$$h_t = o_t \cdot \tanh(c_t). \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the current cell state (c_t) is determined by element-wise multiplication:

$$c_t = f_t \cdot c_{t-1} + i_t \cdot g_t. \quad (9)$$

The forget gate yields a vector f_t with values between 1 (retain) and 0 (forget), which correspond to each node of the input vector x_t . This is done using h_{t-1} from the previous iteration, hence the “short-term memory” from the LSTM model. However, the output gate simply passes the concatenation of x_t and h_{t-1} to yield the o_t vector which is fed into the current h_t and passed on to the next iteration; hence there is also “long-term memory” in the LSTM model.

2.6. Approach 2: Multilayer perceptron (MLP)

The MLP has several hidden layers with fully connected synapses (nodes). In this study, the MLP has one input layer, two fully connected hidden layers, and one output layer (see Fig. 1(b)). The network utilises the “Adam” training optimiser in MATLAB (see Section 2.4) for its

Fig. 2. Information flow through LSTM layer. c_t is cell state at iteration t , h_t is the hidden state output at iteration t , $t-1$ denotes information from the previous iteration, x_t is the current input variables for iteration t . The gates are denoted as follows: forget gate (f), retain gate (i), cell candidate gate (g), and output gate (o).

Table 1

Adjusted training parameters for each model from the Adam optimiser algorithm. Where α is the learning rate (constant), μ is the gradient decay factor (constant), and N is the number of iterations during training.

Optimised	Model		
Parameters	MLP	LSTM	NARX
α	0.05	0.012	0.081
μ	0.9	0.9	0.9
Shuffle	none	none	none
N	700	1,000	10,000

flexibility so that the comparison between MLP and LSTM networks could be made more obvious. The Adam optimiser is often used because of its ability to implement an adaptive learning rate. However, for simplicity of analysis, the learning rate was kept constant. The complete training parameters are displayed in Table 1.

The effective implementation of any NN requires experimentation with key components, or hyperparameters, of the architecture. For the MLP, the key components were the hidden layer (HL) size, number of nodes within each HL, learning rate α , and number of iterations (N). This experimental phase can be difficult because the parameters may be sensitive. Generally, a model that works well with low sensitivity to these parameters is much easier to fit. The selection of values for the parameters was conducted under trial and error. Each parameter was determined based on a balance between the model performance metrics and computational cost. The models were assessed as potential BMSs; therefore, the model should be highly efficient — suitable for scaling up for real-life applications. The same process was applied to the determine the parameters of the LSTM and NARX seen in Table 1

2.7. Approach 3: Nonlinear autoregressive with exogenous input (NARX)

The NARX model predicts the output data using delayed input data. In this case, NARX uses a 1:2 time-step delay. That is, the NN uses the inputs from sample $s-1$ to predict the sample s output. The NARX NN in this study was constructed using the MATLAB Deep Learning Toolbox. The parameters of the NARX model were adjusted according to Table 1. Excluding the time-delay component, the NARX model in this case works like the FNN model with one HL.

3. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

EIS is a powerful and non-destructive technique for investigating the battery lifetime, electrochemical mechanisms, material transport properties, reaction kinetics, behaviour of porous electrodes, and SOC/SOH estimation. The response of the system to a periodic AC signal at a specified range of frequencies with a small amplitude was investigated. In

Table 2

Specifications of the investigated Samsung INR18650-35E cells.

Parameter	Value
Nominal Capacity	3.40 Ah
Nominal Voltage	3.60 V
Maximum Voltage	4.20 V
Minimum Voltage	2.65 V
Nominal Charging Current	1.70 A
Nominal Discharging Current	8.00 A

the galvanostatic mode, the current is measured at the applied potential in the frequency domain. The impedance (Ω) can be derived from the ratio of the voltage-to-current amplitude and the phase lag of the output and input. The impedance can be split into the real part ($\text{Re}(\Omega)$) and imaginary part ($\text{Im}(\Omega)$), which can be represented in Nyquist plots (Fig. 3(a)), from which great insight can be gained [40–44]. The x -axis represents the real part of the impedance, while the y -axis illustrates the negative value of the imaginary part of the impedance. The high-frequency region indicates the Ohmic resistance of the battery, the mid-frequency semicircle signifies the double-layer capacitance effect, and the low-frequency tail is attributed to the diffusion processes within the active material of the battery.

4. Experimental design

In this section, the details of the experimental procedure are outlined systematically, including the specifications of the equipment and items used throughout. The section also describes the manipulation of data in preparation for its use in NN models.

4.1. Experimental methodology

The Li-ion batteries considered in this study were commercial cylindrical cells INR18650-35E produced by Samsung. The anode material is based on graphite and the cathode material is based on lithium-nickel-manganese-cobalt-oxides (NMC). The specifications of the Samsung INR18650-35E cells are listed in Table 2.

The measurement methodology was set up as follows:

1. Two cycles using a charging and discharging current of 0.1C;
2. Measurement of EIS every 25% of SOC in a range of 0–100% SOC during charging and discharging at 0.1C;
3. Cycling of the cell using a charging and discharging current of 0.5C for 50 cycles using 80% of the voltage range;
4. Repeat every 50 cycles: two cycles using a current of 0.1C and measurement of EIS every 25% SOC during charging and discharging at 0.1C.

Fig. 3. (a): Typical Nyquist plot the Li-ion battery at 25 % SOC. (b): Degradation of Samsung INR18650-35E Battery Cell Over Period of 100 Cycles charged and discharged at 0.5 C. (c): Changes in charging and discharging curves for Samsung INR18650-35E cell for a capacity check before EIS measurement at 0.1 C before cycling, after 50 cycles, and after 100 cycles. (d): Comparison of Samsung INR18650-35E cell EIS curves measured at 0% SOC before cycling, after 50 cycles, and after 100 cycles.

A ZKETECH EBC-X battery tester was used for battery cycling. The EIS measurements during 0.1C cycling were performed at the Biologic VMP3 measurement station in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 30 mHz with a voltage amplitude of 10 mV. It is helpful to note here that the above procedure yielded measurements made before cycling, after 50 cycles, and after 100 cycles; thus, three cycles worth of EIS, voltage, and capacitance data were used for the modelling of the LIB SOC (as seen in all the figures of the supplementary data).

The temperature was held constant at 22 °C. throughout the entirety of the experimental procedure. Therefore, the results obtained from the experiment are valid for 22 °C. There was no validation of the results at different temperatures.

4.2. Experimental data

Experimental data from Samsung INR18650-35E cells with NMC chemistry, as described above, were used in this study. The degradation of the cell charged at 0.1 C and discharged at 0.5 C during 100 cycles is shown in Fig. 3(b). The initial discharge capacity was 2.66 Ah, and after 100 cycles, the capacity decreased to 2.41 Ah, representing a capacity retention of 90%. At the end of cycling, the battery cell did not reach its end-of-life.

Two cycles at 0.1 C for charge and discharge were performed before cycling, after 50, and 100 cycles. The first cycle was a pre-conditioning cycle to reset the ‘cumulative history’ of the cell, and the second cycle was a measurement of the actual charge and discharge capacity prior to the EIS measurement at different SOC. The second charge and discharge cycles with regard to battery degradation are illustrated in Fig. 3(c). The discharge capacity at 0.1 C before cycling was 3.38 Ah, and in a capacity check after 100 cycles, the capacity decreased to 3.29 Ah.

A comparison of the EIS curves measured during battery ageing at 0% SOC is depicted in Fig. 3(d). The curve shape is consistent during degradation; however, the main difference is the increase in the ohmic resistance with battery degradation. Note also that an increase in ohmic resistance is observed before cycling and after 50 cycles, but demonstrates stability between 50 and 100 cycles, as seen in Fig. 3(d).

4.3. Data processing

The size of the experimental data used for this study is coarse compared to many NN research papers related to SOC estimation [45–50]. Typical research papers have published comparisons and performances of LIB models using datasets with hundreds or thousands of battery cycles. The dataset in this study includes 69 samples sourced from three battery charge/discharge cycles. A ‘sample’ refers to an observation at a specific instant, otherwise interpreted as a row in the total dataset where each column represents a variable (thus, a 69×7 matrix is the dataset for this study). This study provides a comparison of three NNs designed to model the SOC of a commercialised LIB. The results of this study provide a good reference for each model’s ability to effectively learn underlying patterns with a small dataset. The measured input variables in this study include the charge and discharge voltage (V^+ and V^- , respectively), and the real and imaginary parts of the impedance ($\text{Re}(\Omega)$ and $\text{Im}(\Omega)$, respectively). EIS was not measured in near-continuous discretised steps, such as the voltage and charge. Rather, it was measured at specific SOC intervals throughout the cycle: 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% SOC. Each EIS measurement yielded an array of $\text{Re}(\Omega)$ and $\text{Im}(\Omega)$ values corresponding to an array of spectroscopy measurement frequencies. NNs require an equal number of samples for the input and output by design; therefore, the EIS data were organised such that three samples of 0% SOC EIS data were

Table 3

The architecture and network parameters that gave optimal output accuracy when using 50% data for training.

LSTM			
Hidden Layer	LSTM Layer	Iterations	Learn rate (α)
50	4	1000	0.012
MLP			
Hidden Layer 1	Hidden Layer 2	Iterations	Learn rate (α)
3	2	700	0.05
NARX			
Time Step Delay	Hidden Layer 1	Iterations	Learn Rate
1:2	10	10000	0.081

stacked forming a total of 69 readings (~ 23 measurements at each 0% SOC cycle), and concatenating this with 69 samples of the voltage and charge readings taken at even intervals throughout the full three cycles. The reason for using only EIS measured at 0% SOC is explained in Section 5.2.

Furthermore, normalisation by *max-scaling* is performed on each feature of the dataset individually. The purpose of this is to map all variables to the set $S \in [-1, 1]$ in which the sigmoid function can be successfully applied. The max-scaling technique had greater success in increasing the output accuracy compared to other normalisation techniques such as linear scaling.

5. Results and discussion

In this section, the three proposed ML approaches will be compared with experimental data to evaluate their accuracy and efficiency. It is worth mentioning that the accuracy of each technique depends heavily on the percentage of data considered for training and validating the models. Therefore, the accuracy and adaptability of all techniques will be tested by considering different ratios of datasets. In addition, the sensitivity analysis for each model involves varying the value of the learning rate α and the hidden layer sizes. Furthermore, there are deviations from the parameter specifications in Table 1.

5.1. General performance

The different architectures of MLP, LSTM, and NARX NNs present various limitations and advantages. The three NN architectures work effectively and within typical error bounds when operating with a training size $\geq 70\%$ (≈ 49 samples or more). However, reducing the training size to 50% affects the performance of every technique to different extents. The quantitative SOC output obtained for each model is shown in Fig. 4(a). One can observe that it is difficult to visualise the accuracy of different approaches. Therefore, the relative errors (absolute difference between the experimental and model values, all divided by the experimental values) obtained using different approaches were estimated and are shown in Fig. 4(b). The results reveal that the MLP shows more accurate results than the LSTM and NARX techniques. In addition, the training parameters and architectural designs (quantitatively) with optimal parameters for each model are displayed in Tables 1 and 3; with the respective performance statistics displayed in Table 4. Again, the quantitative analysis demonstrates that the MLP approach outperforms both LSTM and NARX techniques. This is likely due to the more simplistic nature of the MLP applied to a simple dataset and the ability of LSTM to detect more subtle underlying patterns. However, the nonlinear autoregressive with exogenous input (NARX) NN shows less accuracy than both MLP and LSTM in terms of predicting the SOC (see Fig. 4).

5.2. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data relevance

NN architectures typically require data to have inputs and outputs of the same length. In this study, the total data length was 69. The voltage and capacitance observations were made far more frequently

Table 4

Comparison of performance metrics between MLP, LSTM, and NARX models using the mean absolute error (MAE), adjusted coefficient of determination (Adj. R^2 or Adj. R-squared), and standard deviation of error (SD) for each model.

Statistic	LSTM	MLP	NARX
SD	0.0328	0.0318	0.0595
Adj. R^2	0.990	0.999	0.947
MAE	0.0328	0.0098	0.0357

than the impedance spectroscopy, but the data were compressed to align with the fewer impedance values. Impedance spectroscopy was only observed under five conditions: when the state of charge was equal to 100%, 75%, 50%, 25%, and 0%; hence, EIS was recorded five times during charging and four times during discharge. EIS was measured across a spectrum of 23 different frequencies (100 kHz to 30 mHz) and repeated at the aforementioned SOC values. However, the EIS observations showed a deviation between the different SOC values owing to the lithiation/delithiation of the electrode materials. Therefore, a correlation matrix was used to determine which SOC yielded the highest correlation between EIS and SOC.

The EIS analysis outlined the significance of the SOC value when EIS is measured. Table 5 shows that the EIS measured when SOC = 0% has the greatest correlation to the SOC prediction and yields the highest accuracy when implemented into the MLP model. This is a result of the specific internal properties observed at 0% SOC. Therefore, only the 0% SOC EIS data seen in Fig. 3(d) are used in the model; all other EIS data can be found in the supplementary material. The purpose of selecting fewer EIS measurements is to reduce the number of input features, simplify the model, and improve performance.

Furthermore, other studies have shown that the specific frequencies in EIS are related to specific internal components of the battery. Generally, the EIS Nyquist plot displays the three key internal components of the battery. Fig. 3(a) shows the characteristic curve that relates to the following components: The intercept along the horizontal axis by the semicircle relates to the Ohmic resistance of the battery and corresponds to high-frequencies; the semicircle, itself, is representative of the double-layer capacitance effect and corresponds to mid-frequencies; and the diffusion process of the battery cell material is indicated by the straight tail to the right of the semicircle and corresponds to the low-frequency EIS [51].

However, in this case, to arrange the data such that all variables had the same length, the 23 EIS values recorded at 0% SOC before cycling, after 50 cycles, and after 100 cycles were ordered sequentially and yielded 69 samples. Therefore, the voltage and capacitance were compressed to fit the 69 samples. This shows that the EIS measured once per cycle at 0% SOC can produce highly accurate SOC predictions. A recent study by Buchicchio et al. [52] measured EIS at multiple intermittent periods within the battery SOC cycle, making the experimental process very time-consuming. However, the results stipulated above reject the necessity of requiring more than one EIS measurement per cycle. This result is similar to that observed in Babaeiyazdi et al. [51] and further suggests that EIS measured at mid-high frequencies is more strongly

Fig. 4. (a): Comparison of SOC outputs for LSTM, MLP and NARX models against the experimental results. (b): Comparison of mean absolute errors (MAE) for LSTM, MLP, and NARX models. This was the result of 50% of the dataset being used for training.

Table 5
Model accuracy when using the EIS measured at different SOC values.

MLP		
EIS measured at:	Adj R-squared	RMSE
100% SOC	0.991	0.0253
75% SOC	0.991	0.0263
50% SOC	0.995	0.0195
25% SOC	0.996	0.0176
0% SOC	0.999	0.0108

correlated to the SOC than the EIS measurements at lower frequencies, depending on temperature.

These results can be used to significantly reduce the experimental labour for obtaining battery data for SOC prediction by reducing the number of recorded observables. Reducing the number of input variables also reduces the computational cost of the ANN model.

5.3. Computational costs

The testing of different ML approaches is done in terms of computational cost. Varying the number of layers, number of activation functions (neurons) in each layer, and type of activation considered has a significant impact on the computational costs of ML approaches. The computational costs of an ANN can be presented as the total duration of time or as the number of computations performed in the network. The latter is more complicated but provides a more generalised value independent of computer processing power and initialisation costs. The number of computations per iteration (or epoch) can be approximated as the number of nodes (synapses) plus the number of neural paths (connections) that connect them. Multiplying this by the number of iterations in training yields the approximated computational cost in terms of the number of computations. This eliminates the differences owing to the coding layout and format between each model. However, it assumes that all computations are the same; that is, applying the **tansig** or **tanh** function to a vector represents the same computational cost as multiplying the vector by single-valued weights. This limitation is overcome by assuming that most models have a similar ratio between complicated and simple computations.

The MLP, LSTM, and NARX NNs have computation times that are less than 1 min. This was due to the size of the dataset used in this analysis. The comparison of duration in seconds and the number of computations between each model have contradicting results in Table 6 because of the difference in coding structure and functions used in MATLAB. The initialisation of each model is different and has a significant contribution to the total run time because of the relatively

short training duration. Therefore, the approximate number of computations should be regarded as a more accurate representation of the computational cost differences between models.

With this noted, the MLP has the lowest computational cost among the three models. However, LSTM has a similar approximate number of computations and a significant difference in duration. The reason the LSTM has a longer duration than NARX is partly due to the different initialisation processes; however, it may also be noted that the LSTM will have a greater number of complicated computations compared to the NARX. This is because the LSTM layer in the LSTM model duplicates the input vector and applies four activation functions (Eqs. (4), (5), (6), and (7)) through the four gates, as demonstrated in Section 2.5.1 and Fig. 2.

It is worth noting that the values recorded in Table 6 are obtained from the optimal model configuration. When testing the effect of different learning rates (α) in the following section, the computational cost was much greater to allow the convergence of the error curve.

5.4. Pattern recognition and sensitivity of learning rate

The learning rate (α) is a value that signifies the significance of the error produced after each iteration and is thus directly linked to the correction step sizes that the model applies to the weights per iteration. Consistent and high performance for a large range of α values is characteristic of flexible and adaptable NN model structures. MLP and LSTM exhibit good performance for a larger range of α than the NARX model. None of the three models can fit a model with $\alpha \gtrsim 1$. The results from the different learning rates for each model are tabulated in Table 7. Beyond the observations from Fig. 5, there are two more interesting points. First, the LSTM error curve (Fig. 5b) is smoothed when α decreases, which represents the ability of the LSTM model to detect more subtle underlying patterns/trends in the data when given a smaller learning rate and granted a much larger number of iterations for training (and computational cost exceeding 10 min). Second, the NARX model (Fig. 5c), while initially exhibiting the same behaviour as the LSTM, eventually reaches a turning point where the error begins to increase for $\alpha \lesssim 10^{-4}$. However, the MLP model (Fig. 5a) does not exhibit either of these characteristics; rather, it remains relatively unhindered by a decrease in α . LSTM has the most complicated processing of data owing to the LSTM layer. The LSTM layer is primarily focused on uncovering long- and short-term relationships and patterns and assigning a degree of significance to each. This process is likely to be the cause of the success of LSTM in subtle pattern recognition.

To this extent, the NARX NN demonstrated the highest sensitivity to the learning rate. The LSTM NN has the most effective relationship with α , and the MLP NN demonstrates the lowest sensitivity to α , but does not indicate an ability for α to make significant improvements in the model accuracy.

Table 6
Computational cost of MLP, LSTM, and NARX models in [(number of computations) × (Number of iterations)] and elapsed time (seconds) of the complete training process with N iterations. Values were recorded using the 50/50 training/testing ratio and optimal training parameters (TABLE 1).

Model:	MLP	LSTM	NARX
Approximate number of computations	(70) × (700)	(1100) × (1000)	(26) × (10000)
Total Training Duration (seconds)	5	11	3

Fig. 5. Error plots for different learning rates, α , on the MLP (a), LSTM (b), and NARX (c) models.

Table 7
Performance in RMSE and MAE for each model using decreasing α as seen in FIGURE 5.

MLP		
α	RMSE	MAE
5	0.2692	0.2322
0.5	0.0247	0.0201
0.00005	0.0302	0.0246
LSTM		
α	RMSE	MAE
1.2	0.2692	0.2322
0.12	0.0247	0.0241
0.00012	0.0138	0.0109
NARX		
α	RMSE	MAE
8.1	0.4362	0.3620
0.81	0.0182	0.0110
0.081	0.0275	0.0200
0.00081	0.0973	0.0648

5.5. Analysis of model generalisation to unseen data based on data size

The ratio between the training and testing dataset portions had a significant impact on the accuracy of each model output. The impact of varying the training size of each model’s dataset is summarised in Fig. 6 by plotting the changes in RMSE 6(a) and SD 6(b). This shows that the MLP model is the least sensitive to reducing the training size compared to the LSTM and NARX models. MLP recognising the relationships between input and output variables for smaller datasets suggests superior generalisation abilities. Furthermore, the size of the

dataset is most impactful to the NARX model’s ability to generalise to unseen data, demonstrated by the greatest decrease in performance when the size of the training data was decreased.

In Table 8(b), the performance of the LSTM model is consistent and highly accurate when more than 25% of the data are used for training. This is significant because 25% of the total dataset comprises 18 samples, which does not make a full cycle. Therefore, LSTM successfully modelled the SOC of the battery without data to explain the behaviour of a full cycle. However, the RMSE increased significantly from 0.0267 to 0.1630 when the training size decreased from 25% to 20%. The changes in the relative error of the LSTM model output are highlighted in Fig. 7(b). Similarly, the data in Table 8(a) show that the MLP NN successfully predicts the SOC when using 20% or more of the data for training.

In other words, the 14 samples used in the training process allowed the MLP NN to predict the following 53 samples with an RMSE of 0.0189 and an SD of 0.0312. The decrease in accuracy for MLP is highlighted by the jump in the SD from 0.0312 to 0.1906 when the training size decreases from 20% to 15%. This change is evident in the relative error plotted in Fig. 7(a). By contrast, the NARX NN did not exhibit flexibility with respect to the training/testing ratio. Table 8(c) shows the lowest acceptable model accuracy when the training data is 50% of the total dataset. Therefore, the NARX NN demonstrated the least flexibility with training data sizes. This deficiency is clearly presented in Fig. 7(c).

This behaviour is a strong indication of the ability of the ANN model to understand the key relationships between the input and output datasets. The MLP and LSTM models recognise the key patterns and

Table 8

Statistical values of model accuracy for the MLP (a), LSTM (b), and NARX (c) models when training with different ratio between training and testing of the dataset.

(a)							
MLP							
% training	70	50	40	30	25	20	15
RMSE	0.00779	0.00907	0.00730	0.00512	0.00736	0.01890	0.03700
Adj. R^2	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.995	0.989
SD error	0.0305	0.0314	0.0346	0.0509	0.0753	0.0312	0.1906

(b)							
LSTM							
% training	70	50	40	30	25	20	15
RMSE	0.02510	0.03170	0.03500	0.03020	0.02670	0.16300	0.18500
Adj. R^2	0.992	0.987	0.984	0.989	0.994	0.874	0.012
SD error	0.0242	0.0399	0.0456	0.0402	0.0928	0.5491	0.3188

(c)							
NARX							
% training	70	50	40	30	25	20	15
RMSE	0.04320	0.06420	0.08200	0.18800	0.16100	0.14800	0.08270
Adj. R^2	0.973	0.950	0.773	0.471	0.438	0.324	0.491
SD error	0.0284	0.0573	0.2533	0.1196	0.3316	0.2297	0.2959

Fig. 6. Graphical representation of the RMSE and SD from the data found in Table 8. The RMSE of each model when using different training data sizes is plotted as a continuous line with standard deviation (SD) represented as the respective colour shadings. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 9

The effect of changes to the HL sizes of the MLP, NARX, and LSTM architecture highlighted in statistical error measurements. HL1 and HL2 refer to HLs 1 and 2 respectively, LSTM refers to the LSTM layer of the LSTM model.

Model	HL1	HL2	LSTM	MAE	RMSE	SD
MLP	2	2	n/a	0.0309	0.00902	0.03171
	2	20	n/a	0.0312	0.00967	0.03207
	20	2	n/a	0.0322	0.01190	0.03216
	20	20	n/a	0.0324	0.00726	0.03183
	100	20	n/a	0.0294	0.01760	0.06868
	20	100	n/a	0.0541	0.00228	0.03525
	100	100	n/a	0.0307	0.00953	0.03085
	250	250	n/a	0.0354	0.00505	0.04723
	300	300	n/a	0.0306	0.01010	0.03135
LSTM	2	n/a	2	0.0300	0.0319	0.0409
	25	n/a	2	0.0343	0.0384	0.0504
	50	n/a	2	0.0287	0.0251	0.0364
	75	n/a	2	0.0360	0.0462	0.0582
	300	n/a	2	0.0688	0.0397	0.0475
	50	n/a	4	0.0636	0.0706	0.0734
	50	n/a	8	0.0706	0.1100	0.1611
	50	n/a	16	0.1150	0.1610	0.2459
	50	n/a	30	0.1516	0.2030	0.2608
50	n/a	90	0.1270	0.1800	0.2372	
NARX	2	n/a	n/a	0.0892	0.106	0.1304
	10	n/a	n/a	0.0488	0.076	0.0791
	50	n/a	n/a	0.0633	0.097	0.1000
	100	n/a	n/a	0.0769	0.101	0.1290

Fig. 7. Comparison of the output error per sample when using various ratios of training and testing dataset portions in the MLP (a), LSTM (b), and NARX (c) models. The results were obtained by increasing the training portion (% of total) of the data in 5% increments. Here, the highest training % with bad results and the lowest training % with good results are displayed in each graph along with a very good (coloured) reading from each NN for comparison. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

behaviours of the dataset with much less training data compared to the NARX model. Both LSTM and MLP are highly capable of identifying underlying patterns in the cyclic dataset without being given a full cycle of data for training. This is a direct indication of the LSTM and MLP models' success in generalisation to unseen data. The NARX NN requires significantly more training data to recognise the key behavioural trends and patterns in the dataset, specifically, more than one cycle, and in this case, at least 50% of the data for training. The NARX does not present good generalisation to unseen data, contrasting to the MLP and LSTM.

5.6. Hidden layer size impact

The size of the HL is determined by the number of nodes/synapses that it contains. Figs. 8(a), 8(c), and 8(e) display the deviations of the predictions from the exact outputs due to changes in the HL sizes of each model respectively. However, it is difficult to clearly see the extent and significance of these deviations; thus, Figs. 8(b), 8(d), and 8(f) present the relative error plots for each change in HL size, highlighting the significance of each result. The subfigures of Fig. 8 indicate the existence of an optimal size for the HLs of the ANN. This is particularly obvious in Figs. 8(e) and 8(f); the NARX model reaches a maximum accuracy of MAE = 0.0488 (Table 9) when the HL contains 10 nodes. The accuracy decreases when the HL is larger than 10 nodes, owing to the overcomplexity of the NN architecture. Alternatively, MLP does not

demonstrate signs of over-complication. The SOC output and relative error do not differ significantly when the MLP HLs have either 300 or 2 nodes each. The MLP shows great flexibility with HL sizes, as their alterations have very little impact on the output accuracy of the model.

LSTM also exhibits an interesting case of over-complication. The LSTM layer size refers to the number of hidden units within the LSTM gates, as described in Section 2.5.1. The LSTM layer is very sensitive to overcomplications in this dataset. The number of nodes in the LSTM layer gates shows a significant decrease in the output accuracy as the LSTM size increases from four to eight hidden units. This means that the LSTM model fails to utilise a much larger amount of stored information in an efficient way. However, with a fixed LSTM layer size, the LSTM NN demonstrated an optimal HL size of 50 nodes and a decrease in accuracy when the HL had 300 nodes. Therefore, the LSTM layer and HL of the LSTM NN are prone to over-complication.

The MLP demonstrates superior flexibility in the variance of HL sizes. The LSTM layer of the LSTM model is extremely sensitive, although it could perhaps be a simple parameter to determine as a factor between 0.5 and 2 times the number of inputs, for example. This provides an interesting question for further research. The NARX model is also sensitive to the change in HL size, although only moderately sensitive compared to LSTM and MLP.

Fig. 8. Changes in the output of MLP (a), LSTM (c), and NARX (e); and the error of the output for MLP (b), LSTM (d), and NARX (f) plotted for each change in the HL sizes. HL1, HL2, and LSTM in the graph legends are the first hidden layer, the second hidden layer, and the LSTM layer sizes, respectively.

5.7. Overall parameter sensitivities

The MLP demonstrated lower sensitivity to the modelling parameters addressed in the previous subsections. This is because the MLP architecture is simpler than that of the NARX and LSTM models. NARX includes a feedback loop which develops a complicated temporal dependency between the previous and current predictions. This increases the model complexity which provides greater potential for improving the model accuracy; however, for a coarse dataset, the additional complexity of the NARX feedback loop introduces greater sensitivity to the model parameters, making it less robust for modelling with small datasets. Similarly, the inherent complexity of the decision gates integrated into the LSTM layer of the LSTM model increases the complexity of data processing through the NN. While the LSTM layer offers the ability to detect more subtle patterns within the dataset, the increased processing complexity results in a greater risk of misinterpreting input-output relationships, leading to the inclusion of inaccuracies in the

model. This limitation is exacerbated by the insufficient data required to train the model and eliminate any false interpretations from the final model.

The greater complexity of the LSTM and NARX models increases the parameter sensitivity owing to their greater potential for more complex data interpretation. This attribute demonstrated a decrease in model robustness, specifically for coarse datasets. The simple MLP design avoids the inherent sensitivity to the aforementioned parameters when applied to coarse datasets. However, for larger datasets, the heightened complexities of LSTM and NARX may significantly improve the model performance over the simpler MLP.

6. Conclusions

In this study, different ML approaches were used to estimate the SOC of commercial LIBs using EIS measurements. The difference in

architecture between the MLP, LSTM, and NARX NNs has a significant impact on the flexibility of the training and model parameters needed to produce a sufficiently accurate SOC prediction. Specifically, the NARX NN has poor flexibility in terms of the hidden layer size and learning rate. Furthermore, NARX requires at least 50% of the dataset for training to produce an accurate SOC prediction, whereas MLP and LSTM NNs require much less (20% and 25%, respectively). MLP demonstrates the best accuracy and most consistency when comparing variations in the learning rate, training size, and hidden layer sizes. MLP is the easiest model to fit to this dataset and requires the least amount of data to produce a highly accurate prediction of SOC. Unlike LSTM and NARX NNs, MLP does not benefit from a decreased learning rate and fails to identify more subtle underlying patterns and behaviour of the dataset. The LSTM could provide more insight into the behaviour of the dataset; however, the ability to detect more subtle patterns requires a much larger computational cost and does not yield significant improvements and therefore does not perform better than the MLP in general.

The results of this study can be used to aid future researchers in their selection of NN architectures for similar modelling purposes. The material in this paper also provides a summary of the architectural impacts on the performance of the MLP, LSTM, and NARX models. Furthermore, this study demonstrates the ability to accurately model the SOC for LIBs with small datasets, thus reducing the required experimental cost, waste, and labour.

Further EIS analysis can identify the correlation between the EIS frequencies and SOC. The correlation between specific EIS frequencies and SOC observed in the heat maps presented in [51] may indicate a more efficient use of data in NNs by arranging specific frequency impedances as individual input features for the NN. This might allow the NN to draw upon the relationships between the internal structures of the battery to predict the SOC. A better understanding of the internal structures and components that relate to the electrochemical impedance may streamline the EIS measurement process and significantly reduce the amount of unnecessary input data for the selected BMS and NN models. It may be possible to use NNs as a tool to gain insight into the physical phenomena that transpire around EIS and SOC estimation. Perhaps the method of the work completed by [53] can be applied here, with similar results. In addition, other popular NN architectures should be investigated to identify key differences in performance to aid in the selection of appropriate models for SOC estimation for LIBs. Radial basis function NNs and wavelet NNs provide different approaches to modelling SOC and may have key benefits that were not observed in the MLP and LSTM in this study.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mitchell Rae: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Michela Ottaviani:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Dominika Capkova:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Tomáš Kazda:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Luigi Jacopo Santa Maria:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Kevin M. Ryan:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Stefano Passerini:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mehakpreet Singh:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.236929>.

Data availability

The data associated with this manuscript can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/records/13361914>.

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